

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM ON THE PARTICULARLY VULNERABLE TRIBAL GROUP HILL KORWA OF CHHATTISGARH STATE

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ABSTRACT:

This study begins with the understanding of the role that PDS plays on the lives of the identified community; the Hill Korwa tribal people in the north district of Chhattisgarh India. PDS is a major part of India's social security structure with an aimed to deliver food items of necessity among the disadvantaged communities. But it has left undesired impacts: especially in receipt and accruing net advantages by Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) like community of Hill Korwa. In this study, simple random sampling is used to sample 327 respondents from districts of Jashpur, Balrampur, Sarguja and Korba which host the Hill Korwa tribe personal interviews and structured questionnaires are used to collect primary data. However, data obtained from Government sources and other institutional players strengthens the research findings. This according to the research shows that respondents are satisfied with PDS services with 23.85% completely satisfied while 37.00% are... However, 70.03 % of them noted that ration provided to them is inadequate to sustain them throughout the month. Holding 100% awareness among the respondents concerning adequacy of food during lock down the PDS emerged most important during the COVID-19 situation and accordingly, the study indicates that a dependency on PDS is seen among the Hill Korwa where 90.52% has received ration as such during the lock down. More rice was needed by many of the respondents, indicating that in shaping PDS provisions, consideration for the palate and nutritional wants or needs of consumers is crucial.

KEYWORDS:

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HILL KORWA TRIBALS OF CHHATTISGARH

Hill Korwa are primarily a hilly community formed north Chhattisgarh although they can be found throughout the districts of Jashpur, Balrampur, Sarguja and Korba. Korwa of Hill Korwa group was categorized as PVTGs because of having pre-agriculture technology skills with almost nil literacy among them and having stagnant population. By the description given under the Anthropological classification, they fall under the Austro- Asiatic family. The totemistic endogamous segments of the Hill Korwas are five, which are as follows; Edigwar, Ginowar, Hansadwar, Sammathwar and Renla. Hill korwa are a group that hunt, collect forest produce and do Dahiya(slash and Burn) farming, are hunters and forest dwellers and used to live wandering from one mountain to another.¹

The economic life of this tribe was determined by Agriculture activities, Employment, Gathering of fruits and nuts, Hunting amongst others. Nowadays, through their permanent means they have initiated cultivation of crops such as Kodo-Kutki, Godali, Paddy, Maize, Black gram, Green pulse, Kulathi etc. The population which is enumerated in the survey conducted in years 2005-06 according outline of Pahadi Korwa tribes was 34122. Currently, the people of the Korwa tribe have reached 40, 000 people as a whole. In Chhattisgarh, PDS appears to be more effective, with normal entitlements of 35 kgs of rice per household per month at ridiculously low price of Rs or 1/kg for most of the BPL families as per the ration card. The Hill korwa tribals get foodgrains at one rupee per kilogram

foods from the public distribution system because they belong to antyodya or priority card holder. Latterly they are supplied pulses and salt free of cost also they are supplied sugar at 10 rs per kg.

PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM IN CHHATTISGARH

Chhattisgarh Right to Food Act, 2012 right to food act endeavored at providing one's right to food to the populace of the State of Chhattisgarh. This it wants to ensure availability of sufficient amount of food and other necessary nutrient requirements in an economically accessible manner so as to uphold the Right to lead a life with dignity. This Act extends to the whole of the State of Chhattisgarh.

Key points of the Chhattisgarh Food Security Act, passed on December 1, 2012 include:

Legislation Purpose: The act is thus aimed at preserving the TPDS and assisting the state government in representing the effectiveness and works of TPDS.

Support for TPDS: There is state law support for the TPDS and the actions and reforms of the state government to enhance efficiency of the TPDS.

Food Security: Its provides food security to the extent that deserving beneficiaries can afford to purchase the stipulated basic food necessities at low cost.

Affordability: This is because it such food and nutrients should be made available for the people at prices that they

can afford.

ESSENTIAL INFORMATION ON THE PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM IN CHHATTISGRAH

Beneficiaries: To be deserving for food and nutritional aid, the act categorizes various type of beneficiaries of this act. Constituent categories included AAY (ANTYODAYA ANNA YOJANA) card holders, priority and other less privileged households. It is the state government's responsibility to set the details on how to identify the appropriate beneficiaries, the excluded households as well.

ENTITLEMENTS PER MONTH:

AAY and Priority Households: These households are eligible for 2 kg each of iodized salt, black gram and pulses besides 35 kg of food grains at subsidized prices.

General (Non-Poor) Households: It is targeting general households with 15 kilograms of subsidized food grains per months.

Special Groups: The act names certain categories of the population who need extra protection. Such target group comprises; persons below 14 years of age, pregnant and breastfeeding women, the poor, the homeless, students in boarding houses and asrams, the migrant, and needy person during natural disasters.

Implementing Authorities: Local authorities are responsible for various aspects of the implementation, including:

- Identifying eligible households.
- Issuing ration cards to beneficiaries.
- Monitoring and overseeing fair price shops to

ensure the proper distribution of food items.

- Conducting audits of fair price shops to maintain transparency and accountability.

Grievance Redressal Mechanism: It has provided for internal measures for dealing with complaints. These may include call center for help, nodal officer and other means by which beneficiaries can seek help. Moreover, the Chhattisgarh Public Service Guarantee Act, 2011 treats the provision of the above-mentioned entitlements to there eligible households as a service and hence there is provision for service delivery accountability.

Reforms to TPDS (Targeted Public Distribution System): The act outlines a series of reforms to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the TPDS. These reforms include:

- Doorstep delivery of all food items to fair price shops.
- Application of information and communication technology for transparency and to prevent diversions.
- Utilization of "AADHAR" for unique beneficiary identification.
- Ensuring full transparency in records.
- Diversification of commodities available under the PDS over time.
- Maintenance of an adequate buffer stock of food items to address fluctuations in supply.

Sr.No.	Family	Food	Monthly Entitlement	Rate
1.	Antyodaya Family	Rice	35kg per month	Re 1 per kg
		Gram	2kg per family	Rs 5 per kg
		RefinedIodized Salt	In Scheduled Area 2kg per family;In Non Scheduled area 1 kg per family	Free
2.	PrathmikFamily	Rice	10kg per month in 1 member rationcard; 20kg per month 35kg per month in 3 to 5 memberration 7kg per month in 5 member ration card	Re 1 per kg
		Gram	2kg per family	Rs 5 per kg

		Refined IodizedSalt	In Scheduled Area 2kg per family in non-Scheduled Area 1 kg per family	Free
3.	General CategoryFamily	Rice	10kg per month in 1 member ration card and 20kg per month in 2 memberration 35kg per month in 3 to 5 member ration card	Rs 10 kg per

Source: (CG Economic Survey 2021-2022)

CHHATTISGARH STATE FOOD COMMISSION

The Chhattisgarh State Food Commission was constituted on 31st March 2017 as per Govt. of India consensus. It was setup as per the Section 16(1) of the National Food Security Act, 2013 and as per the provision of Rule 8(a) of the C.G PDS (Internal Grievance Redressal) Rules, 2016. The Chhattisgarh State Food Commission is primarily involved with the coordination of the food security and distribution legislation through compliance and completion of the National Food Security Act. This includes redress of complaints concerning distribution of food articles and the efficient working of PDS in the state. The creation of such a commission is helpful to achieve transparency and accountability to food security projects and to defend the rights of the targets.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Hill Korwa, in the state of Chhattisgarh, is one of the PVTGs and fulfills all four central criteria as determined by Government of India for PVTGs. Some of them are; the population density is falling, the community is extremely poor, few people get education, and the community has a meager economy. (Ministry of Tribal Affairs).

Sarala(2015) In the same year, Sarala noted that tribal people of our country are calorie and mineral deficient with low intakes of calcium, vitamin-C, riboflavin and protein. Also she elaborated that the tribal people of our country are also suffering from more extent of undernutrition. According to Khan & other (2018) social, economical & demographic characteristics of the hill Korwa tribe are alarming.

Chakma (2020) Chakma while observing in the period of lockdown in 2020 predicted that these tribal community who are living in the interior Justin bed areas would be of distressing stage if local administration fails to promptly come forward to take necessary measures to supply items of 'Do Piyaja' like the food grains among others. These tribal populations are already struggling with hunger and malnutrition, however, the measures like the lockdown which thus restricted mobility and the return of the migrant workers out of the states, withdrawal from the accessibility to employment and other opportunities worsened the hunger situation in the tribal regions.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the Impact of Public Distribution System(PDS) among Hill Korwa tribalcommunity.
2. To examine the dependence of Hill Korva tribal community upon State sponsored PDS.
3. To analyze performance of PDS among Hill Korva tribal community members in response to COVID-19 lockdown.

METHODOLOGY

DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

1. The study area of this research is situated in the northern region of the Indian state of Chhattisgarh, encompassing the districts of Jashpur, Balrampur, Sarguja, and Korba. Sampling
2. In the study a total of 327 respondent shave been selected from the 4 districts Jashpur, Balrampur, Sarguja, and Korba, where the Hill Korwa tribals reside. Simple random sampling has been applied to the study for the collection of data.

Data collection

1. This study relies on Primary data obtained from personal interview and survey, as well as secondary data through government reports, and surveys conducted by educational institutions and organizations.

OUTCOMES OF THE STUDY

OVERVIEW OF THE POPULATION

Household Demographics: Description of the Demographic characteristics of Respondents

The survey question was answered by more male respondents (92.35%) with 92 of them being 302 individuals, while the number of female respondents was much lesser (7.65%) and they were 25 of 327 participants in this study.

The distribution of age of the respondents in the survey is as follows: "60>" account for 72 (22.02 %), "26-30" for 68 (20.80%). The "36-40" and "41-45" age groups also took their share in the list with 12.54% (41 individuals) and 11.31% (37 individuals), accordingly. Participation by Age

and Gender As for the age group, the youthful age bracket of “<20” had the least representation, with only 4 of the participant, 1.22%, while the “21- 25” age group had 30 participants, 9.17%.

The respondents for the survey had distinct educational backgrounds throughout the study. The largest group of respondents had “Illiterate” status with 56.88% (186 respondents); “Only primary” level of education was responded by 19.88% of the total [65]. Respondents with “middle” education level were 13.15% (43 respondents), “high” and “higher secondary” was 7.03% (23) and 3.06% (10) respectively. Unfortunately no respondents falling in the category of graduate or an anganwadi worker were found in the study.

The respondents’ distribution based on their marital status also showed that 95.11% belonged to the married status; no respondent fell under the unmarried status. And the rest being a widow or widower.

Of all the respondents belonging to the family, the largest group is constituted by the “Medium(4-6)” family size having 46.79% (153 respondents) followed by “Small(1-3)” group of respondents which is 30.28% (99 respondents). The “Large(7-9)” subcategory level represents only 19.57% (64 respondents) while the “very large(<9)” subcategory level only represents 3.37% (11 respondents).

Geographic Variables: Accessibility to PDS outlets

The study was conducted across 40 villages in 4 districts of Chhattisgarh. Out of the total 40 villages, 100% (40) are covered under the PDS service, while none of the villages are uncovered.

PDS COVERAGE

Proportion of Tribal households covered by the PDS.

Out of the 327 respondents, information on ration cards showed that of the respondents 93.88% (307) possess ration cards. On the other hand, those who said that they don’t have ration cards comprised of only 6.12% (20 respondents). This data is useful in establishing the probability density of possessing a ration card in the cross-sectioned populace.

Among all the total respondent with Ration cards 91.74% (300) response with Below poverty line (BPL) ration cards, while only 2.14% (7) response with Above poverty line (APL) ration cards.

Access to PDS outlets

According to the PDS service, 100% (40) villages fall under the coverage category while no village falls in the not covered category out of 40 villages in the study area.

Among the 327, who possess ration card the 30.88% of them (101) said that they received ration from the office of Sarpanch/Secretary, 40.37% of the respondents (132) stated that they received ration from the Co-operative society and 22.63% of the respondents (74) received ration from the Female self-help group. Moreover, 6.12% (20) sample of respondents replied that they didn’t have ration cards with them.

PDS PERFORMANCE

PDS Performance:

Beneficiaries' satisfaction with the PDS services.

Among the total respondents possessing Ration cards, maximum 23.85% confirm that they are fully satisfied with the ratios being provided to them, 37.00% of them report partial satisfaction, likewise, 33.03% majority their dissatisfaction while 6.12% of the respondents do not possess ration cards.

Adequacy of food items provided by the PDS.

Additional research on whether ration provided for the whole month is enough 23.85% respondent find it sufficient while 70.03% do not. Only 10.09% said that ration is adequate for 20-25 days, and 2.75% for more than 25 days.

Timeliness and regularity of PDS distributions during the pandemic.

93.Many (88%, 307) said that they continue to received their ration well from the village administration. Further 6.12% (20) of respondents stated that they did not have ration cards.

From a total of 327 respondents with Ration cards, 83.76% of the total 274 reported receiving portions monthly while 274 reported receiving portions once in two months (on a monthly basis) giving 7.03% while 10 reported receiving portions once in three months (on a monthly basis) 3.06 percent.

COVID-19 IMPACT

COVID-19 Impact:

Incidence of COVID-19 cases within the Tribal population.

According to the data, 327 respondents (100%) reported that none of their family members or village members have been infected with COVID-19.

Food Security

All 327 respondents reported that their family received proper nutritious diet during the COVID- 19 lockdown, indicating a 100% availability of proper nutrition.

Dependence on PDS:

Household reliance on PDS for essential food items during the pandemic.

The majority of respondents (90.52%) received the ration uninterrupted during the lockdown. Only a small percentage of respondents (0.92%) had some problem in acquiring ration,

About 70,03 % of respondents stated that they need extra rice apart from that offered as ration. Slightly more than three-quarters of respondents receiving extra rice said that they needed 15 kg or less (76.67%); 23.24% said they needed another 15 kg. The prime minister argued that this signifies that while a tiny portion of the patients requires more than 15 kilograms of rice, about 28.33 percent of the respondents need additional rice.

A significantly greater number of respondents, 156 in number (63.61%), said they had bought rice at a price between 10-20 Rs/Kg. Still fewer respondents, 6.12% availed rice at a price within higher range of 20-30 Rs/Kg while only 0.31% respondents bought rice at more than 30 Rs/Kg. The remaining 29.97% denied purchasing anything from the rice from the external market thus indicated that they only relied on the ration issued by the government.

POLICY VARIABLES

Policy reforms concerning the functioning of the Public Distribution System. Surely, more than half of the respondents were satisfied with the PDS as 96.64% of the respondents had no grievance against the PDS. On bureaucrats, only 2.45 percent of the respondents had complaints against them while on the system on PDS only 0.92 percent of respondents had complains. That how ration is distributed, issue of ration card and complexity in it especially the aadhar card included.

The findings also show that more respondents demanded provision of milk for children 100%, followed by the provision of egg 185%, wheat flour/wheat 185 % and to also likely the quantity of rice given 170% . Here, it should also be stressed that participants were able to indicate more than one answer; therefore, the sum of response percentages is above 100%.

The last item of importance was kerosene oil; 301 respondents (92.05%) demanded its provision. Kerosene oil is widely used for cooking and lighting in our homes particularly in the rural areas where there is most likely little access to electricity.

CONCLUSION

The present research investigation was undertaken with the following purpose: To assess the working of the PDS in relation to the availability, accessibility, and affordability of necessity food articles in the identified Hill Korwa tribal households. The review established that most of the tribal families sampled had been receiving ration without any disruption. However, a small percentage of the households had issues with ration that they received, several households had no ration card. Regarding the availability of rice, the target group consumed rice on average 10-20 days per month, moreover, 60% of respondents need

10-30kgs of rice per month. A greater percentage of respondents bought rice from the external market at Rs. 10-20 per kilogram. With regards to other foods consumed by respondents, priorities included milk for children, eggs, wheat flour, kerosene oil etc. The assessment of PDS revealed that most of the households are within a range of 1-5 km from the fair price shop. However, few of the households have mentioned problems regarding travelling time, distance and waiting time to reach the fair price shop. Also, the study realized that most of the respondents were dissatisfied with the quality of rice received from PDS. Able state that the cost of PDS was found to be acceptable by majority of the respondents with majority of them spending less than Rs. 2000 on basic food items per month. However, a number of respondents experienced expenses that limit them from affording these basic goods and services; a larger portion reported needing subsidies fully to cater for them. In general, the findings imply that PDS is a vital channel of managing food security for households. However, there are areas that require enhancement with regard to the quality of rice to be supplied, number of fair price shops, and financial support to households in the vulnerable groups.

Remark: The research paper based on the findings sponsored by ICSSR New Delhi.

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